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ABSTRACTS

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Valorization of sawdust for enhanced lignin modifying enzymes production and correlated degradation of endocrine disrupting chemicals using *Pleurotus ostreatus*

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Abstract: Increased industrial and agricultural activities, globally, has resulted in the exponential release of hydrophobic emerging pollutants, categorized under endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) which alter the endocrine and homeostatic systems both in humans and animals at each trophic level even at low concentrations (ng/L). The physical or chemical methods for elimination of these EDCs are either costly or add more toxic secondary metabolites into the environment. Hence, an eco-friendly approach involving white rot fungus (WRF) having an ability to valorize lignocellulosic waste with production of cocktail of lignin modifying enzymes (LMEs) - Laccase, Lignin peroxidase (LiP) and Manganese peroxidase (MnP) proves effective as it catalyzes multiple enzymatic reactions to mineralize such hydrophobic EDCs. With this perspective, inoculum of five days grown WRF isolate showing 99.68 % homology with *Pleurotus ostreatus* was used for EDCs (50 ppm) degradation by incorporating BPA / TCS in minimal salt medium (MSM), pH 5 valorized using 5% saw dust. Enhanced degradation of 90.46% BPA and 86.64% TCS observed in 20 days can be correlated with enhanced expression of laccase (247.22 U/L; 308.33 U/L), LiP (193.54 U/L; 405.01 U/L) and MnP (7.81 U/L; 18 U/L) respectively. Besides degradation potential, WRF also showed plant growth promoting traits with Indole acetic acid production (6.2 µg/ml), ammonia (1.23 µmol/ml), siderophore (43.36 %) and ACC deaminase activity (0.49 mM/ml). Adsorption studies of BPA conducted using composite beads of autoclaved fungal biomass (obtained after degradation experiments), sodium alginate and fly-ash showed maximum adsorption of 13.61 mg/g at 5th hour.

Keywords: Valorization, lignin modifying enzymes, endocrine disrupting chemicals, white rot fungi.

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